

Scorpiops reini **sp. n.**, female paratype with 2nd offspring

Scorpiops reini sp. n., left patella external, female paratype (above) and male holotype (below)

Scorpiops lowei, male 1

Scorpiops lowei, male 2

Scorpiops lowei, female 1

Scorpions lowei, female 2

Scorpions lowei, female 3

Scorpiops puerensis, male 1

Scorpions puerensis, male 2

Scorpions puerensis, female 1

Scorpions puerensis, female 2

Scorpions puerensis, female 3

Scorpions puerensis, juvenile female 1

Scorpions shidian, male 1

Scorpions shidian, male 2

Scorpions shidian, male 3

Scorpions shidian, male 4

Scorpions shidian, juvenile male 1

Scorpiops shidian, juvenile male 2

Scorpiops shidian, female 1

Scorpions validus, male 1

Scorpions validus, male 2

Scorpions validus, female 1

Scorpiops xui, male 1

Scorpiops xui, male 2

Scorpions xui, female 1

Scorpions xui, female 2

Scorpions xui, female 3

Scorpiops yangi, males 1 and 2

Scorpiops sp. (aff. *vachoni*) from Yinchangxiazhai

DNA materials

Scorpiops yangi, male

Scorpiops xui, juvenile male

More photos of examined Yunnan species available on Facebook

Scorpiops jendeki: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1AcuH9CmTg/>

Scorpiops lowei, male: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1BANjsP7gS/>

Scorpiops lowei, female: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/152UCMYfWc/>

Scorpiops lowei, validus: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/19fXaQ6stx/>

Scorpiops xui, male: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/15XZUtDkYT/>

Scorpiops xui, female: <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1B3GmKtHJo/>

Scorpiops xui (2023): <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/18VzzPMPLx/>

Scorpiops yangi (2023): <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1519HAANpY/>